

Supp. Figure 1. Locations of tubes within a parcel belonging to either of our locational classes. The orange arrows represent hair tube locations we would consider to be non-wooded. The yellow flower represents an ornamental plant. The purple arrows indicate hair tube locations we designated as wooded. Wooded locations could be both inside or outside of a parcel.

